

Hybrid Ceramic Polymer Electrolytes Enabling Long Cycling in Practical 1 Ah-Class High-Voltage Solid-State Batteries with Li Metal Anode

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Solid polymer electrolytes offer a safer alternative to organic liquid electrolytes in high-voltage lithium metal batteries, yet challenges remain in achieving adequate cyclability, energy density, scalability, and safety. This study presents the cycling performance of 1 Ah high-voltage lithium polymer batteries featuring a hybrid ceramic polymer electrolyte (HCPE), a lithium metal anode, and a $\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$ (NMC-811)-based positive electrode. The HCPE stands out for its remarkable mechanical properties, with a Young's modulus exceeding 200 MPa at room temperature, providing robust resistance against dendrite formation. The Li||Li symmetric cells exhibited outstanding performance, cycling for over 1000 hours at a capacity of 2 mAh cm^{-2} , highlighting the exceptional attributes of HCPE. Full cell testing is conducted under practical conditions, utilizing various cell configurations, from coin cells to large pouch cells with a 1 Ah capacity, achieving an energy density of nearly 250 Wh kg^{-1} and promising cyclability with 80% capacity retention after 110 cycles. The study also investigated thermal runaway characteristics, showing comparability with commercial lithium-ion batteries. This research underscores the scalability and performance of high-voltage lithium metal polymer batteries, advancing their potential for commercial viability.

1. Introduction

In the race to address climate change, it is necessary to transform the source of energy consumed. In this regard, electric vehicles (EVs) are in the spotlight. Today, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are the undisputed technology for powering EVs. However, controversies regarding safety and the need for a longer cycle life and vehicle autonomy open the roadmap to new technologies. A cost-effective, sustainable, durable, safe, and high-energy chemistry that avoids scarce raw materials will revolutionize the EV benchmark.^[1] In particular, new chemistries are being investigated to increase the energy density of the batteries.

On the cathode side, high voltage active materials, such as nickel-rich layered oxides ($\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z\text{O}_2$ – NMC, or $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Co}_y\text{Al}_z\text{O}_2$ – NCA, with $x+y+z = 1$ and $x \geq 0.6$) provide higher energy density compared to low voltage cathode active materials, such as LiFePO_4 (LFP, nominal voltage

(NV) = 3.4 V versus Li/Li⁺).^[1–3] On the anode, lithium metal, with a specific capacity of 3860 mAh g^{-1} and the lowest reduction potential (–3.04 V versus the standard hydrogen electrode, SHE), is considered as one of the most promising negative electrode materials for automotive applications.^[4,5] However, the application of these aggressive chemistries is not exempt of drawbacks. For instance, the use of highly reactive lithium metal anode accelerates battery degradation and poses safety concerns, owing to the growth of lithium dendrites and to the consequent risk of short circuits, among other issues. For these reasons, the application of lithium (Li) metal anodes is conditioned by the improvement of the coulombic efficiency of the plating/stripping process, by the possibility of hindering Li dendrites growth, and by a general improvement of the safety in case of internal short circuit.^[4] One of the main strategies to improve the safety of Li metal batteries consists in replacing liquid electrolytes with solid-state electrolytes (SSEs), which are believed to outperform liquid electrolytes in terms of flammability, leakage, and volatility.^[6] Solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs), in which an alkali-metal salt is dissolved in a polymer matrix, form a particularly

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interesting class of SSEs, owing to their high flexibility and good processability.^[7–9] Poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) is the reference polymer matrix for SPEs. PEO-based SPEs have excellent compatibility against Li metal, but their ionic conductivity is too low for application at room temperature. In addition, polyether based SPEs have relatively low oxidative stability at operational temperature,^[10] especially in combination with layered oxide cathode materials,^[11,12] which ultimately limits their use with high voltage cathode active materials.

Owing to the need of safer, high-energy density batteries for automotive application, in recent years there has been an increasing effort to develop high-voltage, lithium metal polymer batteries (HV-LPBs). Several strategies have been applied to enhance the electrochemical stability of polymer electrolytes. In particular, the use of alternative polymer hosts with higher oxidative stability, also in multilayer configurations, has given promising results.^[13–19] Beside this, coating strategies and interface engineering have been applied both at the anode and at the cathode interfaces to hinder Li dendrites growth, preserve the polymer electrolyte from degradation, and ultimately to enhance the cycle life of HV-LPBs.^[20–25]

Thanks to this huge effort, a substantial improvement in the performance of HV-LPBs has been achieved, with increasing number of studies reporting full cell cycling with polymer electrolytes and high-voltage cathode materials,^[10] sometimes with cycle life up to hundreds of cycles.^[23,26–29] Nonetheless, sufficient cyclability in practical cell configurations (i.e., with high cathode loadings and thin metal anodes) has been rarely demonstrated, and the issue of Li dendrites growth has not yet been solved. The latter is obviously related to the area capacity, as higher areal capacities imply higher current densities at equal C-rates, which in turns results in inhomogeneous lithium plating and possible dendrites growth. Thus, it is not surprising that the reported cyclability generally decreases with the cathode loading, and that most of the studies reporting good cyclability data with HV-LPBs use very low cathode loadings, sometimes below 1 mAh cm⁻².^[10] The cathode loading is a particularly relevant parameter, as it affects the energy density of the cells, which is the main drive for the development of this technology. Without demonstrating cyclability at relevant cathode loadings (>2 mAh cm⁻²), HV-LPBs will not be able to compete with commercial LIBs in terms of energy density. Some recent studies have attempted to address this issue, by targeting cathode active material loadings above 10 mg cm⁻²,^[30–44] corresponding to an areal capacity of 2 mAh cm⁻² for a specific capacity of 200 mAh g⁻¹. In most of the cases, however, the electrolyte is a gel-polymer electrolyte, possibly cross-linked, comprising large quantities of carbonate-based liquid electrolytes or other solvents (gel-polymer electrolytes are defined as containing ≈40 wt.% of liquid electrolyte).^[45] Gel-polymer electrolytes have far better cycling performance than solid polymer electrolytes, thanks to the higher conductivity, but the addition of flammable liquid components reintroduces some of the safety issues which prompted the development of solid electrolytes.

Another issue regards the scalability of HV-LPBs. Conventional LPBs with 3 V-class cathodes (such as LFP) have been successfully scaled up and even commercialized,^[46] but this is not the case for HV-LPBs, owing to the lower level of maturity for this technology. Obviously, owing to the large amount of mate-

rial and expensive equipment necessary for the upscaling, most research studies report cycling data obtained in coin cells or at best in monolayer pouch cells. Only a limited number of studies have reported cycling data for HV-LPB multilayer cells. In the already cited study by Zhang et al., the performance of a LiNi_{0.8}Mn_{0.1}Co_{0.1}O₂ (NMC-811)||Li multilayer cell with capacity of 2.8 Ah is reported.^[40] To the best of our knowledge, this is one of the first studies in which performance of multilayer HV-LPB is reported, although the electrolyte in this case is a carbonate-based gel-polymer electrolyte, with a similar composition to common liquid electrolytes. Other recent articles reported the performance of multilayer cells with polymer electrolytes and high-voltage cathodes.^[47,48] In these cases, however, the cells employ graphite anodes, and therefore cannot be regarded as HV-LPBs. In general, HV-LPB cycling performance is rarely validated at multilayer cell level, which casts doubt on the scalability of this technology. Furthermore, there is almost no reliable data about the safety of these cells (besides some basic nail penetration test or flammability test), as abuse tests require large, well performing cells with a capacity of at least 1 Ah. Safety data, however, are particularly important due to the presence of Li metal anodes and the associated risk of internal short circuit and thermal runaway.

Based on these premises, we analyze here the cycling performance and safety characteristics of HV-LPB multilayer cells, based on a) a polyether-based hybrid ceramic polymer electrolyte (HCPE), with high ionic conductivity and high stability against Li metal, in contact with the anode and functioning as polymer separator and b) a high loading solid state cathode with polymer based catholyte having high oxidative stability. The HCPE layer is further supported on a microporous polyolefin separator, which greatly enhances the mechanical properties of the HCPE and hinders lithium dendrites growth, thus enabling cycling at higher current densities and capacities. We tested the performance of this composite polymer electrolyte in HV-LPB cells, with Ni-rich layered oxide cathode material (NMC-811), demonstrating cycling in large multilayer pouch cells with 1 Ah capacity (high cathode area capacity of 2.7 mAh cm⁻², thin Li metal foil anode with thickness of 20 μm per unit cell), obtaining a capacity retention of over 80% after 100 cycles (60% after 200 cycles), obtained under relatively harsh testing conditions, namely at 60 °C, and with voltage range of 3.0 – 4.2 V, meaning 100% depth of discharge. Furthermore, we evaluated the safety of the 1 Ah cell by overtemperature test, showing that the proposed HV-LPB has comparable safety characteristics to commercial LIBs, despite having a Li metal anode. This study shows the possibility of obtaining good cyclability in relevant conditions on a large HV-LPB cell and constitutes thus an important step in the advancement of high-energy, high-voltage solid-state battery technology.

2. Results and Discussion

The hybrid ceramic polymer electrolyte (HCPE) used in this study is composed of a poly(propylene oxide-co-ethylene oxide) copolymer (p(EO-PO)), cross-linked poly(ethylene glycol) diacrylate (PEGDA), poly(ethylene glycol) dimethyl ether (PEGDME) as polymeric plasticizer, and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) as lithium salt (Figure 1). The addition of a plasticizer was required to compensate the decrease of ionic conductivity induced by

Figure 1. Scheme of the HCPE and of a corresponding NMC-811||Li bilayer pouch cell.

the cross-linker, which, in turn, proved necessary to stabilize the mechanical properties of the HCPE at high temperatures and to enhance the resistance to dendrites growth. In any case, the choice of a high molecular weight polymeric plasticizer ensures that the HCPE retains the transport and thermal stability properties typical of solid polymer electrolytes. Additionally, the polymer electrolyte matrix contains dispersed $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Al}_x\text{Ti}_{2-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (LATP) micrometer-sized particles. These enhance the mechanical properties of the HCPE, the resistance to Li dendrites growth, and modulate its long-range charge transport properties, as reported in a previous study.^[52] Finally, the HCPE is supported on a microporous polyolefin separator, to further increase the resistance to Li dendrites growth and enable cell cycling at high areal capacities. Consequently, two layers can be distinguished, a proper HCPE layer containing the LATP particles, and an underlying full-polymer layer infiltrated in the polyolefin separator pores. Cross-section SEM images of the HCPE are reported in Figure S2 (Supporting Information). In full cells, the HCPE layer faces the cathode, thus the contact between Li metal and the LATP particles is avoided. In the cathode pores, a gelled electrolyte/binder (catholyte), with different composition, ensures the ionic transport within the cathode pores and the mechanical integrity of the cathode layer. As-prepared HCPE membranes were first characterized, to determine their thermo-mechanical, transport and electrochemical properties, and then used as separators in Li||Li symmetric cells and NMC-811||Li cells.

2.1. Thermo-Mechanical and Transport Properties of the HCPE

A high thermal stability is a prerequisite of solid electrolytes. The polymeric plasticizer used in the proposed HCPEs, PEGDME, has a high molar mass (500 g mol^{-1}), therefore, high thermal stability can be anticipated. The thermal properties of the HCPEs were studied by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). In the TGA profile, a two-step degradation is observed (Figure 2a). A first thermal degradation occurs at 250°C caused by the decomposition of the organic components (polymer chain and separator) ($T_{d,5\%} = 276^\circ\text{C}$, Table 1).

This first decomposition accounts for the 65 wt% of the total sample mass. The second decomposition step, at 350°C , is ascribed to the decomposition of the lithium salt, LiTFSI ($\approx 20 \text{ wt}\%$). The residual mass, $\approx 15 \text{ wt}\%$, is composed of LATP particles, which are stable at temperature higher than 600°C .

The DSC profile of the HCPE, between -80 and 100°C , is shown in Figure 2b. The as-prepared HCPE has a glass (T_g) and a melting (T_m) transition at -53 and 20°C , respectively (Table 1). Thus, the HCPE is a semicrystalline material below room temperature. Above 20°C , the HCPE is fully amorphous. In polymer-rich hybrid electrolytes, the ionic conductivity is mainly governed by the polymer chains segmental motion, which in turn is related to the T_g . A high chain segmental mobility promotes ionic conductivity. Thanks to the low glass transition and the low crystalline phase (16 J g^{-1}), high ionic conductivity can be thus forecast. This low semi-crystallinity may be the result of three different phenomena: a) the copolymeric nature of the p(EO-co-PO) main polymer component, as propylene oxide units can hinder the crystallization of the ethylene oxide units; b) the addition of the plasticizer; and c) the interpenetrating network formed by the crosslinked PEGDA, hindering the ordering of the p(EO-co-PO) chains.

The mechanical properties of the HCPE were studied by tensile test. The stress-strain curves show distinct anisotropic behavior (Figure 2c), owing to the anisotropic morphology of the uniaxially-stretched supporting separator. In particular, the HCPE shows higher modulus and fracture stress in the stretching direction of the supporting separator, and slightly higher fracture strain in the transversal direction. The tensile modulus (E)

Table 1. Summary of the thermal properties of HCPE, where $T_{d,5}$ is the temperature at which a 5% mass loss is registered in the TGA, T_g , T_m , and T_c the glass transition, melting and crystallization temperatures, respectively, ΔH_m and ΔH_c the melting and crystallization enthalpies, respectively.

$T_{d,5} / ^\circ\text{C}$	$T_g / ^\circ\text{C}$	$T_m / ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta H_m / \text{J g}^{-1}$	$T_c / ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta H_c / \text{J g}^{-1}$
276	-53	20	21	-14	16

Figure 2. Thermomechanical and transport properties of HCPE. a) Thermogravimetric analysis; b) differential scanning calorimetry; c) stress-strain curves from tensile tests in longitudinal and transversal direction, with respect to the stretching direction of the supporting separator; d) ionic conductivity between 20 and 80 °C, as a function of the inverse of the temperature (temperature in °C in the top axis); e) typical chronoamperometric profile of a Li||Li cell polarized at 0.01 V at 60 °C, used for determination of the transference number T^+ ; f) EIS spectra collected before and after the potentiostatic polarization experiment at 60 °C. The size of the semicircle is used to calculate the interface resistance with Li metal at 60 °C, indicated in the figure.

was calculated from the initial slope of the stress/strain curves. In general, the HCPE shows high tensile modulus (>100 MPa in both directions, **Table 2**), higher than most unsupported polymer electrolytes.^[53] Correspondently, the fracture toughness (the integral of the stress/strain curves) is also very high, especially in the stretching direction of the supporting separator. The latter is obviously the origin of the excellent mechanical properties of

Table 2. Summary of the mechanical properties of HCPE from the tensile tests, where E is the tensile modulus, namely the initial slope of the stress/strain curves in Figure 2c, and U_T is the fracture toughness, that is, the integral of the stress/strain curves. σ_{fin} and ϵ_{fin} are the fracture stress and strain, respectively, namely the maximum stress and strain sustained by the sample before fracturing.

	E / MPa	σ_{fin} / MPa	ϵ_{fin}	U_T / MPa
Long.	270	40	1.4	50
Trans.	200	4	2	8

the HCPE, although the composite electrolyte has lower tensile modulus and fracture stress than Celgard (Figure S3, Supporting Information) owing to the higher thickness. For comparison, the unsupported HCPE showed modulus below 1 MPa and fracture toughness below 2 MPa.^[52] Thanks to these peculiar mechanical properties, high resistance against dendrites growth is foreseen for this HCPE.

The ionic conductivity between room temperature and 80 °C was measured by impedance spectroscopy (Figure 2d). At room temperature, the ionic conductivity is $2.3 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, increasing to $2.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 80 °C. At the reference temperature of 60 °C, the ionic conductivity is $1.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. The conductivity profile versus the inverse of the temperature shows a slight curvature, indicating Vogel-Tamman-Fulcher behavior, typical for amorphous polymer electrolytes. There are no observable discontinuities in the conductivity profile, in agreement with the results of DSC, which predict amorphous behavior over 20 °C. The ionic conductivity is negatively affected by the presence of the microporous separator, and is comparable to the

conductivity of non-plasticized, amorphous polymer electrolytes, typically showing ionic conductivity between 10^{-5} and 10^{-4} S cm $^{-1}$ at room temperature.^[53] Such values of conductivity predictably allow cycling at temperatures higher than 50 °C, at moderate C-rates. The Li $^{+}$ transference number (T^{+}) at 60 °C, determined by potentiostatic polarization method (Figure 2e,f), is relatively low, being comprised between 0.1 and 0.2. Calculation by Bruce-Vincent method (Equation 2) gives a T^{+} of 0.18, whereas calculation by Watanabe method (Equation 3) gives a slightly lower value of 0.14. Low values of transference number are common in dual-ion conducting polymer electrolytes and the obtained values are in the expected range for this type of material. The interface resistance with Li metal at 60 °C is ≈ 30 Ω cm 2 (Figure 2f), stable over time and upon cycling in the applied potentiostatic polarization conditions. This indicates that the electrolyte has a good chemical and electrochemical compatibility with Li metal, despite the presence of LAMP particles which are unstable in contact with Li metal. The observed stability is attributed to the presence of a polymer coating layer covering the LAMP particles and avoiding contact between LAMP and Li metal. Finally, the restricted salt diffusion coefficient (D) at 60 °C is $3.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m 2 s $^{-1}$ (Figure S4, Supporting Information). By applying the Nernst-Einstein equation^[54] with this value, an ionic conductivity of $\approx 10^{-4}$ S cm $^{-1}$ is obtained, thus in fair agreement with the experimental ionic conductivity. This indicates good dissociation of the lithium salt, as expected for LiTFSI. The transport mechanism in LAMP-containing HCPEs and the role of LAMP particles were analyzed in detail in a previous study.^[52] The results showed that the interface resistance between ceramic particles and polymer phase decreases with the temperature, and that, at 60 °C, Li $^{+}$ exchange across the two phases occurs, although it is relatively sluggish. At this temperature, the LAMP particles are expected to contribute to the long-range charge transport process. However, the overall effect on the ionic conductivity and on the lithium transference number is marginal, given the relatively low concentration of the LAMP particles (5 vol%). The main expected effect of LAMP particles is to enhance the mechanical properties and the resistance to Li dendrites growth.

2.2. Plating/Stripping Performance in Li||Li Cells

The resistance against Li dendrites growth was further studied by plating-stripping in Li||Li symmetric cells at 60 °C (Figure 3). First, the limiting current density was determined by cycling the cells galvanostatically at different current densities, with plating/stripping capacities of 1, 2, and 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$. To be noted that these are relevant capacities, close to the typical areal capacities of LIBs and far beyond typical values reported in solid-state batteries. At 1 mAh cm $^{-2}$, voltage instabilities are first observed at a current density of 1 mA cm $^{-2}$ (C/1, Figure 3a), with steady-state overvoltage of ca. 0.1 V at 0.5 mA cm $^{-2}$ (C/2, Figure 3a). At higher plating/stripping capacities, however, voltage instabilities are observed already at 0.3 mA cm $^{-2}$ (C/6 and C/10 in Figure 3b,c, respectively), with steady-state overvoltage of ca. 50 mV at 0.2 mA cm $^{-2}$ (C/10 and C/15 in Figure 3b,c, respectively). The decrease of the limiting current density with

the capacity clearly shows the deleterious effect of increasing amount of plated lithium and confirms the importance of conducting the plating/stripping experiments in relevant conditions. The long-term plating/stripping behavior was further analyzed by galvanostatic cycling in Li||Li cells at constant current density of 0.1 mA cm $^{-2}$, with plated/stripped capacity of 1, 2, and 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$ (Figure S5, Supporting Information, Figure 3d,e respectively). The cells showed good cyclability up to a capacity of 2 mAh cm $^{-2}$. At this capacity, the voltage profiles are stable up to ca. 1000 h (25 cycles), with an overvoltage of ≈ 30 mV (Figure 3d). Subsequently, the voltage started increasing progressively, with increasing initial polarization, accompanied by an increase of the concentration polarization during the stripping half cycles. The failure is attributed to progressive degradation of the electrolyte and of the electrolyte/electrode interface. The cell finally went into a short circuit after ≈ 1400 h. For comparison, a cell was cycled also at higher capacity of 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$ (Figure 3e). Also in this case, the initial steady-state overvoltage was of 30 mV, but it started to increase earlier, after 500 h, and short circuit was observed at ≈ 900 h. As in the previous experiments at lower capacity, short circuit is preceded by an increase of both initial and concentration polarizations. Altogether, the plating/stripping experiments suggest that the HCPE can sustain relatively high cathode loadings, such as 2 and 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$, provided that the current density during charge does not exceed 0.2 mA cm $^{-2}$. This excellent plating/stripping performance is obtained thanks to the use of the microporous polyolefin separator as an additional diaphragm. Indeed, plating/stripping experiments with unsupported HCPE, cycled with a plated/stripped capacity of 1 mAh cm $^{-2}$, showed voltage instabilities already at 0.33 mA cm $^{-2}$ (Figure S6a, Supporting Information), and cells cycled at constant current density of 0.1 mA cm $^{-2}$ showed voltage instabilities, due to soft short circuit, already after less than ten cycles (Figure S6b,c, Supporting Information).

To further investigate the evolution of the membrane and the “Li/membrane” interface upon cycling, three symmetric Li||Li cells were cycled for 10 cycles at 60 °C, with a constant areal current density of 0.1 mA cm $^{-2}$, varying the specific capacity to 1, 2 and 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$, shown in Figure 4a–c. The voltage profiles of the cycles depend on the amount of Li being stripped or plated. For instance, at 1 mAh cm $^{-2}$ the cell polarization is stable and only increases slightly at the end of the sequence. When increasing the areal capacity to 2 and 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$, there is a more pronounced increase in the polarization which is most evident for the cell cycled at 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$. This increase in polarization was previously ascribed to degradation of the electrolyte or the electrolyte/Li electrode interface. The impedance spectra acquired after cycling (Figure 4d) indicate that the interfacial resistance remains relatively unaffected by cycling, the most prominent change is an increase in the bulk resistance of the cell cycled at 3 mAh cm $^{-2}$. To further investigate in detail the changes of the Li||Li cells, the cells were disassembled and analyzed. All cells were assembled in the same way, so that the last plating occurred on the side facing the polyolefin separator (LAMP-free side). In all cells, the lithium electrode attached to the HCPE side (stripped side) is well integrated into the electrolyte and impossible to remove. For the 2 mAh cm $^{-2}$ sample this also applies to the lithium electrode attached to the separator side, however, the

Figure 3. Plating/stripping experiments in Li||Li symmetric cells, at 60 °C. Limiting current density determination with plated capacity of a) 1 mAh cm⁻², b) 2 mAh cm⁻², and c) 3 mAh cm⁻². The labels indicate the C-rate C/N, where C is the capacity and N is the plating/stripping time. The asterisk in red indicates the C-rate/current density at which the first voltage instabilities are observed. Long cycling at constant current of 0.1 mA cm⁻², with plated capacity of d) 2 mAh cm⁻² and e) 3 mAh cm⁻².

1 and 3 mAh cm⁻² samples the lithium electrode can be removed from the separator side of the membrane. Pictures of the lithium electrode facing the separator side and of the separator side itself are shown in Figure 4e. The surface of lithium electrode cycled at 1 mAh cm⁻² is smooth and shiny, whereas the sample cycled at 3 mAh cm⁻² is rough and covered by darker areas. The

difference in adhesion of the lithium electrode can be explained by the fact that only limited penetration of lithium deposits into the electrolyte layer occurs at 1 mAh cm⁻², whereas lithium filaments are incorporated into the electrolytes at 2 mAh cm⁻². These filaments are converted into dead lithium when the capacity is increased further, which enables the lithium metal to

Figure 4. Plating/stripping experiments in Li||Li symmetric cells, at 60 °C. Three cells cycled with the same current density but for different times to set the capacity of the cells to a) 1 mAh cm⁻², b) 2 mAh cm⁻², and c) 3 mAh cm⁻² for 10 cycles; d) EIS measurements for the cells cycled in a–c), normalized to the surface area of the Li-metal electrode; e) Pictures of the polyolefin separator side of the membrane (LATP-free) and the Lithium metal facing this side of the 1 and 3 mAh cm⁻² cells after cycling and disassembly; SEM top view images of the Li-metal electrode surfaces of the f) 1 mAh cm⁻² and g) 3 mAh cm⁻² shown in e).

be removed. Indeed, lithium metal is also visible on the separator in the sample cycled at 3 mAh cm⁻². The surface of the Li anodes facing the separator side were then investigated by SEM and the acquired images can be seen in Figure 4f,g. A clear difference can be seen in the morphology of the Li anodes: the latter is smooth when cycled at 1 mAh cm⁻², while at 3 mAh cm⁻² there are both rough and smooth domains on the surface. The rough surface can explain the increase in polarization and suggests the formation of dead lithium and dendritic deposits. In the 1 mAh cm⁻² sample, layers can be observed on the surface of the lithium while for the 3 mAh cm⁻² this is less obvious. This layer could be explained by the formation of a Li rich organic composite layer which later is incorporated in the uneven growth of lithium filaments.

To further investigate the interfaces between the Li metal anode and the electrolyte, the Li|HCPE|Li stacks shown in Figure 4e and a reference pristine cell were investigated by SEM and EDS. Cross-sections were prepared by cryogenic ion milling and handled in a transfer chamber to minimize the

contact with air. The SEM images, and the phases of the cross-sections are shown in Figure 5. The SEM spectra of the different phases depicted in the phase mapping are reported in Figures S7–S9 (Supporting Information). Other SEM images of the pristine cell are reported in Figure S2 (supporting Information).

From the cross-section micrographs in Figure 5a–c it is obvious that the membrane undergoes drastic changes during the cell cycling, depending on the capacity stripped and plated. The cross-section SEM of the uncycled cell in Figure 5a shows clearly the two layers of the HCPE, that is the microporous polyolefin separator and the underlying HCPE layer encompassing the LATP particles, with a thickness of ≈70 μm (100 μm in total). The cross-section shows a thin layer between the separator and the lithium electrode, caused by the electrolyte penetrating through the microporous separator, before the crosslinking. The adhesion on the polyolefin separator side is worse than on the LATP side. Regarding the state of the cycled cells at the time of disassembly, the last plated side corresponds to separator side (upper part in the SEM

Figure 5. Cross-section analysis of Li||Li cells with HCPE electrolyte: a) pristine b) cycled ten times at 60 °C, at a current density of 0.1 mA cm⁻² and with a plated/stripped capacity of 1 mAh cm⁻² and c) cycled ten times at 60 °C, at a current density of 0.1 mA cm⁻² and with a plated/stripped capacity of 3 mAh cm⁻²; the corresponding phase map for each sample is shown in d–f).

images). In the cross-section of the cell cycled at 1 mAh cm⁻² (Figure 5b) the two layers of the HCPE can still be clearly distinguished. However, close to the Li surface, some electrolyte degradation is visible, with phase mapping showing these regions to be rich in lithium and oxygen, and small spots of dead Li clusters. The decomposition seems to start in certain areas on the Li foil first while others remain unaffected. When increasing the capacity to 3 mAh cm⁻², the changes in morphology are more obvious, although some features are observed, in minor grade, already in the cross-section of the sample cycled at 1 mAh cm⁻². The amount of dead lithium is increased and visible on both sides of the polyolefin separator, but the latter seems to be intact. There are also some new features, not visible in the 1 mAh cm⁻² sample: a new, thick layer (100 μm) is observed on the upper side of the polyolefin separator (Figure 5c). In a more detailed analysis of the composition of this new layer, the phase mapping (Figure 5f) reveals that it consists of three layers. The region closest to the separator is compositionally very similar to the polymer component of the LAMP side while, by moving away from the separator, the fluoride signal becomes less pronounced and oxygen content is increased in the SEI1 and SEI2. However, the change in

the composition is probably more gradual than depicted in the mapping. The lithium content also increases when approaching the edge of this interlayer (Figure S10, Supporting Information), which could be due to the partial integration of the Li foil into the organic interphase which was visible in the photos in Figure 4e. The formation of this interlayer could explain the increased bulk resistivity observed in the EIS spectra (Figure 4d). The EDX phase mapping shows three large LAMP particles embedded into this new interlayer, at the other side with respect to the LAMP-rich layer. However, the corresponding features in the SEM image do not appear as LAMP particles (Figure 5c). In addition, although the phosphorous EDS mapping shows some spurious phosphorous signal distributed in this area (Figure S10, Supporting Information), the latter has much lower intensity than in the LAMP particles, comparable to the intensity of the overhanging SEI layer. This leads us to conclude that the signal originates from the ion milling and might be due to the presence of voids where milled LAMP particles are trapped. The EDS phase mapping erroneously recognizes these clusters as LAMP particles because of the compositional contrast with the surrounding areas, and in particular owing to the presence of traces of phosphorous, titanium, and

Figure 6. Oxidative stability of HCPE and chemical/electrochemical stability in contact with NMC-811 cathodes. a) LSV in SS||Li cells, at 60 °C and 0.1 mV s⁻¹; b) LSV in the low current region. The blue trace is the derivative of the LSV profile; c) EIS spectra of pristine NMC-811||Li cells at 60 °C; d) EIS spectra of NMC-811||Li cells charged at 4.3 V (60 °C); e) Evolution of the bulk electrolyte resistance (R_b in Figure 6d) during 12 h at 4.3 V; f) CV profiles of NMC-811||Li cells at 60 °C, between 3.0 and 4.3 V versus Li/Li⁺. The CVs were collected at 20 μ V s⁻¹; g) Floating current test on an NMC-811||Li cell at 60 °C. The red trace represents the voltage profile over time and the blue trace the current over time.

oxygen, and to the absence or weakness of the typical SEI components signals, such as carbon, fluorine and sulfur. Altogether, the cross-sectional SEM/EDS images clearly confirm the detrimental effect of increasing plated capacity on the morphology of the HCPE.

2.3. Oxidative Stability

The oxidative stability of the electrolyte is important for cycling with high-voltage cathodes and is of great concern for polyether-based electrolytes, especially at high temperatures.^[10] First, the

oxidative stability of the HCPE was evaluated by standard LSV in SS||Li cells. The LSV profile (Figure 6a) shows a steep increase of the current at ≈ 5 V versus Li/Li⁺, indicating breakdown of the electrolyte. However, taking a closer look at the low current region and to the derivative current profile (Figure 6b), a first degradation event is observed already at ≈ 4 V, whereas the onset of the electrolyte final breakdown can be more precisely located at 4.5 V, in agreement with Homann et al., which determined the oxidative stability limit for PEO-based electrolyte at 4.6 V versus Li/Li⁺.^[55] The electrochemical stability of the electrolyte can be negatively affected by the chemical/electrochemical reactivity of the cathode active material, especially in the delithiated (charged) state.^[11,12,24] To investigate the stability of the HCPE in contact with the NMC-811 cathode active material, a series of tests were performed in NMC-811||Li cells. EIS spectra were collected over time both in the discharged and fully charged state (4.3 V). The stability of the EIS spectra in the pristine cell (Figure 6c) confirms the chemical compatibility between the electrolyte and the cathode active material in the lithiated state. At 4.3 V, the bulk electrolyte resistance initially increases, stabilizing after ≈ 5 h (Figure 6d,e), also indicating the formation of a stable interface with the cathode. This result is thus in agreement with the LSV, which predicts limited degradation over 4.0 V versus Li/Li⁺, resulting in the formation of a passivation interlayer, and then continuous electrolyte degradation over 4.5 V versus Li/Li⁺. CV profiles, collected between 3.0 and 4.3 V, show also a relatively stable behavior, with the presence of two intense peaks at 3.8 and 3.5 V which correspond to the reversible delithiation and lithiation of the cathode, respectively (Figure 6f). After the first two peaks, the intensity and shape of the peaks is relatively stable, thus indicating negligible electrolyte degradation. Finally, the floating current experiment (Figure 6g) showed an initial progressive decrease of the floating current, which was attributed to the sluggish charging process of the composite cathode. This reversible process may possibly mask the oxidation of the electrolyte or other parasitic processes. Nonetheless, at 4.5 – 4.6 V the floating current stabilizes at ≈ 50 μ A. This residual current is a possible indication of ongoing electrolyte degradation. Notably, no short circuit was observed up to 5 V, showing that, despite the electrolyte undergoing some degradation, no mechanical failure occurs, thanks to the presence of the polyolefin separator. In conclusion, on the one hand, the floating current test confirms the electrolyte oxidation at voltages higher than 4.5 V versus Li/Li⁺ but does not exclude the occurrence of degradation events at lower voltages. On the other hand, the CV and EIS tests confirm the electrolyte stability at 4.3 V versus Li/Li⁺. Altogether, the results of the electrochemical stability tests suggest that the HCPE should be stable in the operation voltage range of NMC-811, up to at least 4.3 V versus Li/Li⁺.

2.4. Full Cell Performance

The electrochemical performances of NMC-811|HCPE|Li cells, was initially tested with unsupported HCPEs. Preliminary tests were carried out in coin cells, with positive electrodes having active material loading of ca. 5 mg cm⁻², corresponding to an area capacity of ≈ 1 mAh cm⁻². At 60 °C and C/10 (≈ 0.1 mA cm⁻²), the cells showed specific initial capacity well above 200 mAh g⁻¹

Table 3. Optimized cathode composition and features. CAM: cathode active material.

Coating feature	Value	
Formulation	NMC 811	74 wt%
	C45	3 wt%
	Catholyte	23 wt%
CAM loading / mg cm ⁻²	5 / 15.2	
Area capacity / mAh cm ⁻²	0.9 / 2.7 (nominal sp. capacity: 180 mAh g ⁻¹)	
Density / g cm ⁻³	≈ 3.0	
Current collector	Carbon coated Al/C foil (14 μ m thickness, Gelon)	

(Figure S11a, Supporting Information). For comparison values of ≈ 200 mAh g⁻¹ are usually reported for NMC-811 cycled up to 4.3 V versus Li/Li⁺.^[3] At C/5 the specific discharge capacity was still above 200 mAh g⁻¹, whereas it dropped to 180 mAh g⁻¹ at C/3. The steep capacity decrease at C/3 is due to the loss of contribution of the high-voltage plateau, which is shifted to higher voltages, above the cutoff voltage, owing to the higher cell polarization (Figure S11b,c, Supporting Information). In the subsequent long cycling at C/10, a steady capacity is observed, with capacity retention of 80% after 26 cycles, and a capacity fade rate of 0.7% per cycle. In the same range, the average coulombic efficiency was 98.7%. Correspondingly, the profiles of voltage versus capacity showed a progressively increasing slope upon cycling (Figure S11d, Supporting Information), whereas the differential capacity profiles (Figure S11e, Supporting Information) showed a decrease of intensity and a progressive shift of the peaks associated with the plateaus in the voltage profiles to higher and lower voltages, during charge and discharge, respectively. Altogether, this indicates an increase of the internal cell resistance upon cycling and possibly a loss of cathode active material, which might be caused by a degradation of the electrolyte/cathode interface. Another cell cycled at 40 °C showed lower capacity (Figure S12a, Supporting Information), owing to the lower ionic conductivity of the HCPE. The specific capacity at this temperature was still acceptable at C/10 (180 mAh g⁻¹), but it decreased below 100 mAh g⁻¹ at higher C-rates (90 and 50 mAh g⁻¹ at C/5 and C/3, respectively). At room temperature, the cell delivered very poor performance, with specific capacity below 50 mAh g⁻¹ already at C/10 (Figure S12b, Supporting Information).

Despite the good results obtained at 1 mAh cm⁻², attempts to cycle unsupported HCPEs at higher cathode loadings were unsuccessful, owing to the relative softness of the HCPE, high hardness of micrometric NMC-811 powder and to the uncontrollable growth of Li dendrites. For this reason, also based on the results from Li||Li cells testing, further full cell cycling and subsequent scale-up were performed with HCPEs supported by a polyolefin separator. The cathode composition was additionally optimized to enable scaling-up on the pilot plant, and to optimize the cell performance at higher loadings. In particular, the catholyte concentration was increased and the active material fraction was decreased from 80 wt% to 74 wt%, to facilitate ion transport within the solid-state cathode layer (Table 3).

Additionally, the cutoff voltage during charge was reduced to 4.2 V, to improve the cyclability. **Figure 7a** shows the specific discharge capacity and the coulombic efficiency of a coin cell cycled at 60 °C, with cathode loading of 5 mg cm⁻². The initial capacity at C/20 was ≈190 mAh g⁻¹, lower than the one obtained with higher charge cut-off voltage. Relevant specific capacities over 100 mAh g⁻¹ are obtained up to C-rates of C/2, with specific discharge capacities of 170, 150, and 110 mAh g⁻¹ obtained at C/5, C/3, and C/2, respectively (**Figure 7a,b**). The specific capacity and rate capability were slightly lower than those obtained with unsupported HCPE, owing to the lower ionic conductivity of the electrolyte and to the restricted voltage range. In particular, the high-voltage plateau was not observed by reducing the charge cutoff voltage to 4.2 V (**Figure 7b**; **Figure S13a**, Supporting Information). However, the cyclability was improved. At cycle 100, the capacity retention was 82%, normalized on the specific capacity of the first cycle at C/10 (cycle 3). The slight capacity decay is associated with an increase in polarization (**Figure S13b,c**, Supporting Information), which indicates an increase of cell resistance, possibly caused by an increase of the interface resistance between the HCPE and either the cathode or the anode. The cycling performance of the supported HCPE were studied also with high cathode loading, with active material loadings of 15 mg cm⁻², corresponding to an area capacity of 2.7 mAh cm⁻². Cells cycled at 60 °C and C/10 showed specific discharge capacity of ≈180 mAh g⁻¹ and a capacity retention of 88% after 40 cycles (**Figure 7c,d**). Monolayer pouch cells, with an area of 30 cm², showed similar performance, although with slightly lower specific capacity of ≈160 mAh g⁻¹ at C/10 and 60 °C (**Figure S14**, Supporting Information). With the pouch cells, an initial external pressure (torque of 0.3 N m) had to be applied to get good electrochemical performance. The cells showed initial good capacity retention, but in some cases sudden failure or nonlinear capacity fade behavior was observed, probably due to the inhomogeneous Li plating/stripping.

Finally, HV-LPB cells were scaled-up to multilayer pouch cells with nominal capacity of 1 Ah. The electrochemical performance of these pouch cells was assessed at 60 °C. To ensure good contact in the system, the pouch cell was placed between two metallic plates applying a torque of 0.3 N m (≈3 kg cm⁻²), and then tested at 0.1C/0.1C within 3.0–4.2 V cycling range at 60 °C. The discharge capacity and coulombic efficiency results are shown in **Figure 7e**. The developed HV-LPB exhibits a first discharge capacity of ≈0.8 Ah (148 mAh g⁻¹) and a good and stable coulombic efficiency (CE ≈100%) for 200 cycles. The discharge capacity decreases progressively, and after 111 cycles the cell reaches 80% of the capacity retention. Charge/discharge curves presented in **Figure 7f** demonstrate steady decreasing of the charge and discharge capacity that can be attributed to increase of internal resistance and active material loss over cycling, as observed in previous small cell cycling experiments. It must be noted that the initial energy density of the multilayer cell (without casing) reaches 246 Wh kg⁻¹. This value is close to the energy density of state-of-the-art LIBs (≈250 Wh kg⁻¹).

Altogether, the cycling performance obtained in this work is among the best reported so far, for cells having a solid polymer electrolyte and cathode active material loadings above 10 mg cm⁻². As reported in reference,^[10] and shown in **Figure 8** and **Table S1** (Supporting Information), there are only few ex-

amples of cycling performance of HV-LPBs with relevant cell configuration (thin solid electrolyte, cathode with high areal capacity, and thin Li anode), and even less studies showing cycling in multilayer cells. In this study, the cycling performance of HV-LPBs are demonstrated at multilayer pouch cell level, indicating that the results obtained can be translated to practical batteries.

It must be noted that the achieved energy density is still inferior to the one required for automotive applications (400–450 Wh kg⁻¹). The results thus demonstrate how challenging it is to reach these targets for solid-state polymer cells, even by employing a high-energy cell configuration with self-standing Li-metal foils as anodes and a Ni-rich layered oxide as cathode active material. Achieving the target energy densities will require further optimization steps, mainly by a) increasing the discharge specific capacity by increasing the charge cutoff voltage (up to 4.3 or 4.4 V), b) increasing the area capacity towards 4 mAh cm⁻², c) increasing the cathode active material fraction in the cathode (toward 80 wt% or higher), and d) decreasing the thickness of the solid electrolyte (< 50 μm). On the other hand, all these measures must be carefully balanced to limit the resulting negative repercussions on the overall cell performance, in terms of cyclability and rate capability. In particular, the latter is still inferior to Li-ion batteries, as it is in general for solid-state polymer batteries, given the lower ionic conductivity of solid polymer electrolytes. Furthermore, the use of planar Li metal sheets as negative electrodes represents another limit to the achievable rate capability, as the planar geometry allows only relatively low current densities. A substantial improvement of the C-rate capability and decreasing of the operational temperature will probably require the use of structured lithium metal anodes and the use of plasticizers with higher ionic conductivity, that is the shift toward quasi-solid state cell configurations.

2.5. EIS Measurements in Three-Electrode Pouch Cell

The internal impedance of NMC-811|HCPE|Li cells was studied in three-electrode pouch cells. The use of a reference electrode can provide useful information on the cell ageing mechanisms, as it enables to monitor individually the responses from the positive and negative electrodes. Three-electrode setups have been widely reported in the literature in conventional cells with liquid electrolyte to investigate the degradation of the interphases.^[56] However, few studies have been released on the integration of reference electrodes in solid-state batteries.^[57,58]

In this paper, a solid-state NMC-811|HCPE|Li single-layer cell was successfully instrumented with a LFP reference electrode as displayed in **Figure 9a**. The profiles in potential from the first cycle without EIS steps are represented. The potential curves are consistent with previous studies on solid and conventional NMC|Li batteries.^[59,60] The slight shift of electrode potential (≈±0.05 V versus Li/Li⁺) observed at the negative side might be explained by the formation of solid electrolyte interphase between the polymer and the lithium electrode. The open circuit voltage (OCV) value of LFP electrode (3.424 V versus Li/Li⁺) corresponds to the mean value of the plateau potential of the reference (±5 mV) and

Figure 7. Cyclability of NMC-811|HCPE|Li cells, with supported HCPE: a) specific discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis) of a NMC-811|Li coin cell with cathode active material loading of 5 mg cm^{-2} , cycled at 60°C , between 4.2 and 3.0 V; b) selected charge–discharge voltage profiles, at different C-rates, of the same cell; c) specific discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis) of a NMC-811|Li cell with cathode active material loading of 15 mg cm^{-2} , cycled at C/10, 60°C , between 4.2 and 3.0 V; d) selected charge–discharge voltage profiles related to c); e) Discharge capacity (left axis) and coulombic efficiency (right axis) as a function of the cycle number, of a 1 Ah NMC-811|Li pouch cell, with cathode active material loading of 15 mg cm^{-2} , cycled in the following conditions: 60°C , 0.1C/0.1C, 3.0–4.2 V, initial torque of 0.3 N m. The pouch cell is shown in the inset; f) selected cycle charge–discharge curves of the 1 Ah-class pouch cell (discharge capacity shown in e).

Figure 8. Cycle life versus cathode active material loading (CAM) of HV-LPBs with CAM loadings higher than 10 mg cm^{-2} . The cycle life refers to the number of cycles corresponding to a capacity retention of 80%. In the cases in which the cycling was interrupted before reaching this point, the number of performed cycles was used. The numbers in round brackets indicate the initial specific capacity. Reference numbers are indicated in square brackets. Further details (C-rate during charge, cycling temperature) are reported in Table S1 (Supporting Information).

cannot explain the potential shift observed for the negative electrode.

EIS measurements were performed during the initial rest at 60°C prior cycling the cell and during the second cycle at distinct SoC (Figure 9b–e; Figure S15, Supporting Information). Frequency is reported as Frequency (x) = 10^x Hz. EIS profiles from the instrumented cell and a cell without any reference electrode are compared at OCV and after charge and discharge (at 4.1, 4.2, 3.9 and 3 V). The EIS spectra from the three and two-electrodes cells are very similar as they present three main identical resistive contributions, in specific frequency ranges. When compared to other EIS spectra, the EIS profile from the initial OCV step shows only two main semi-circles at high (10^5 – 10^4 Hz) and mid (10^4 –100 Hz) frequencies, and a capacitive slope at low frequencies (100 Hz–100 mHz) as shown in Figure 9b. Upon charging, this latter contribution tends to bend, appearing as a third resistive contribution at low frequency for both the three and two-electrodes cells. From this observation, it can be hypothesized that this low frequency contribution is related to a charge transfer mechanism from the cathode side. The shape of this semi-loop depends on the state of lithiation of NMC-811 and appears as a straight line once the NMC was fully lithiated (such as in initial OCV measurement).^[61] At the end of discharge, a third resistance below 100 Hz is observed instead of the initial capacitive slope which suggests that the NMC-811 cannot be fully lithiated at its pristine state. The increase of the cathode tortuosity or changes of the catholyte/NMC-811 interphase may lead to lower lithiation of the NMC particles.

Besides, the EIS spectra seem to follow identical resistance evolution over cycling, regardless of the presence or not of the reference electrode (Figure 9c–e; Figure S15, Supporting Information). The low frequency contribution, between 100 Hz and 100 mHz, is the most susceptible to evolution. Upon charge, the latter decreases at high potential while it increases upon dis-

charge at lower potentials, except for a slight increase of resistance at 4.2 V. This result further supports previous assumption about the origin of this low frequency contribution attributed to cathode charge transfer resistance. Indeed, the cathode charge transfer resistance is highly dependent on the SoC of the cell.^[62]

The use of the reference electrode leads to a deeper understanding of the origin of all the resistive contributions. Figure 9f shows the EIS spectra from the positive electrode, after initial rest and after charge and discharge. First, a high resistance is observable at low frequencies (100 Hz – 100 mHz), as previously discerned for both the three and two-electrodes cells, at the full cell level. This result confirms that the low frequency contribution is mainly caused by the positive electrode. Furthermore, the SoC of the cell modifies this resistance. Thanks to the use of the reference electrode, we can thus affirm that the low frequency resistance between 100 Hz – 100 mHz belongs to the charge transfer from NMC-811 particles. This assignment is also supported by many examples in the literature, in conventional instrumented LIBs with liquid electrolyte.^[63] The resistance decreases during charge, and it increases during discharge, which is connected to the mechanism of delithiation and lithiation of NMC-811 over cycling.

Figure 9g presents a zoom on the positive electrode EIS spectra, where two other resistive contributions are discernable at high and mid frequencies, in the identical frequency range previously observed at the full cell level with and without reference electrodes (10^5 – 10^4 Hz and 10^4 –100 Hz). Only the second resistance at mid frequency changes during charge and discharge. According to literature,^[64] the resistive contribution at high frequency could be related to contact resistance, for example at the interface between the current collector and the active material in the case of positive electrodes. On the other hand, the contribution at mid frequency could be linked to the interphase between the catholyte and the NMC particles or cathode electrolyte interphase (CEI).^[18] To conclude, the EIS spectra from the positive electrode shows similar resistances than those at the full cell level, regardless of the use of reference electrode, at three specific frequency ranges. The low frequency contribution is mainly caused by the positive electrode at the cell level, due to the charge transfer resistance of NMC particles. The linear part between the mid and low frequencies contributions (100–10 Hz) is related to the tortuosity of the positive electrode, in other words, the ionic diffusion pathways within the catholyte to reach NMC particles.

Figure 9h displays the EIS spectra of the negative electrode after initial rest and after charge and discharge. As before, three main resistive contributions can be recognized. However, the resistances are much less deconvolved at high and mid frequencies. Besides, only the high frequency contribution relies in the same frequency range observed at the full cell and positive electrode levels (10^5 – 10^4 Hz). The second resistance at mid frequency is larger and relies between 10^4 –10 Hz. According to EIS studies on symmetric Li-metal cells,^[65] high and mid frequency resistances could come respectively from the bulk electrolyte resistance and the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) resistance. A third resistive contribution is also observed in the negative EIS spectra, between 1 Hz and 100 mHz. This time, the origin of this low frequency resistance is more challenging to interpret as many discrepancies appear in the literature.^[66] From our results, we can assume that this low frequency resistance tends to evolve over cycling.

Figure 9. Electrochemical responses of a three-electrode solid-state NMC/HCPE/Li single-layer pouch cell. a) Potential profiles from the positive and negative electrodes and cell voltage from the first cycle without EIS steps; comparison of EIS spectra from the instrumented cell and the conventional cell without reference electrode: b) at the open circuit voltage, after 12 h initial rest at 60 °C; c) at 4.2 V, i.e., at the end of charge; d) at 3.9 V, during discharge; e) at 3.0 V, i.e., at the end of discharge (60 °C, 3 kg cm⁻², 0.28 mA cm⁻², frequency (x) = 10^x Hz). Deconvolution of positive and negative electrodes responses in a three-electrode solid-state NMC/HCPE/Li single-layer pouch cell. f) EIS profiles from the positive electrode, after initial rest and after cycling at 4.2 V and 3.0 V; g) Zoom-in on the high and mid frequencies resistive contributions from the EIS spectra of the positive electrode; h) EIS profiles from the negative electrode, after initial rest and after cycling at 4.2 V and 3.0 V (60 °C, 3 kg cm⁻², 0.28 mA cm⁻², frequency (x) = 10^x Hz).

It decreases during charge, when lithium is plating on the negative electrode, while it increases over discharge, when lithium is being stripped. This evolution can be caused by the expansion or roughness change of Li-metal surface over cycling, as observed by postmortem SEM on Li electrodes from cycled symmetric cells (Figure 4).

Finally, by comparing the EIS spectra of the full cell, positive and negative electrodes, the three main resistances can be easily allocated to either the cathode or the anode. The high and low frequency resistances at the cell level appear mainly caused by the positive electrode. On the other hand, the mid frequency resistance is mostly due to the negative electrode. The largest

contribution to the cell impedance is given by the low-frequency resistance, which is associated with the cathode charge transfer resistance. The EIS spectra of three-electrode cells were compared with those of two-electrode monolayer cells with larger size (60 mAh) and with the EIS spectra of multilayer cells. In comparison with single layer larger pouch cells (60 mAh), cycled with the same protocol, some discrepancies can be noted, especially in terms of resistances. Indeed, larger pouch cells show larger resistances at high and mid frequencies when compared to small pouch cells (Figure S16a–d, Supporting Information), but lower resistance at low frequencies. However, the previous three main resistance contributions can be recognized at the same range of frequencies and the contribution at low frequency seems to follow similar resistance evolution than small pouch cells (important increase of this resistance at low potentials). The three main resistance contributions are observed also in the EIS spectra of 1 Ah cells (Figure S16e, Supporting Information), thus confirming that the conclusions of the EIS analysis can be translated also to larger monolayer and multilayer cells.

2.6. Safety Evaluation

In the development of new battery technology (such as solid-state lithium metal battery technology), safety assessments are crucial but rarely carried out.^[67,68] This is because these assessments require an advanced level of technological development. At the very least, high-performance cells of ≈ 1 Ah need to be manufactured for testing under abusive conditions. If the cells are underperforming, e.g., because of too high internal resistance, short-circuit and nail tests will lead to positive results (i.e., no thermal runaway). However, these apparent positive results might be due only to the poor electrochemical performance of the cell. To avoid these biases, in this study we opted for an overtemperature test with a $6\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ ramp.

As shown in Figure 10a, the abuse test is composed of three steps. First, during phase A, the cell temperature increases quite linearly in agreement with the heating system ($6\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) until the thermal runaway initiation temperature (T_{ini}) is reached, at the thermal runaway initial time (t_{ini}). Both T_{ini} and t_{ini} are defined as the moment at which the temperature ramp exceeds $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Then, during phase B, the heating through power supply is stopped and temperature reaches T_{max} by self-heating of the cell during the thermal runaway. Lastly, during phase C, the temperature decreases slowly up to ambient temperature (T_{amb}).

The images in Figure 10b–e clearly show the same evolution as the graph in Figure 10a. At t_{ini} , the thermal runaway starts with the ejection of incandescent particles, probably lithium metal melt. Between 3 and 6 s after t_{ini} , the runaway is at its maximum. From seven seconds after t_{ini} , the thermal runaway slows down considerably, and at this time the cooling phase begins. The image in Figure 10e shows the cell after the thermal runaway. It is clearly visible that the reaction has spread across the entire active surface of the cell. It is also worth noting that the mass of the cell has decreased by 70 wt%.

As shown in Figure 10a, following the temperature ramp, thermal runaway is initiated at a temperature of $147\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This temperature may seem low because the destabilization of NMC-811 electrode generally occurs between 160 and $190\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.^[69,70] Nev-

ertheless, in the case of an overtemperature test on a full cell, the thermocouple is placed on the outer surface of the cell. Thus, self-heating can lead to a significant temperature gradient between the core and the surface of the cell. The work of Charbonnel et al. clearly shows in X-ray radiography that the thermal runaway starts from the core of the cell with a surface temperature between 148 and $159\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.^[71] Under the same overtemperature conditions ($6\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ ramp), this present study on solid-state batteries shows a maximum temperature very close to those presented in this previous paper. Respectively, the maximum temperature for a Li-ion cell with liquid electrolyte (LG HG2) is $821\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, for a reassembled all-solid-state cell $813\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and for the HV-LPB of this study the maximum temperature is $820\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The temperature increase of the copper plates was used to calculate the thermal runaway energy, which is 8 kJ . As the cell tested has a capacity of 1 Ah , the normalized energy is 8 kJ Ah^{-1} . Once again, the energy from the thermal runaway that remains in the cell and is not released with the gas or dust is comparable with the literature data.^[72,73] Finally, the mass of matter ejected during thermal runaway is $\approx 70\%$ of the initial mass, which is in same order with other studies.^[72]

In conclusion, the abuse test showed that the solid-state batteries in pouch cell format developed in this study have similar safety characteristics to commercial LIBs, judged as a positive outcome considering the use of Li-metal anodes and the lack of any external safety device in the former.

3. Conclusions

In this work, solid-state high-voltage lithium polymer batteries (HV-LPBs) are developed, encompassing a bilayer polymer electrolyte, thin Li-metal anode, and a high-voltage Ni-rich NMC-based cathode. A hybrid ceramic polymer electrolyte (HCPE) is used as separator and is composed of a cross-linked and plasticized polyether matrix, LiTFSI as lithium salt, LATP particles, and a microporous polyolefin separator as further mechanical support. This HCPE has high thermal stability, up to $270\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, strong mechanical properties, with Young's modulus above 200 MPa , and ionic conductivity of $1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The electrochemical stability of the HCPE, tested by conventional LSV and by EIS and floating test in NMC-811 || Li cells, reaches at least 4.3 V versus Li/Li⁺. The optimized transport and mechanical properties enable excellent plating-stripping performance in Li || Li cells, with over 1000 h stable plating/stripping at a plated capacity of 2 mAh cm^{-2} and a current density of 0.2 mA cm^{-2} . Postmortem SEM/EDS analysis of cells cross-sections showed that the increasing cycled capacity has a detrimental effect on the separator morphology, with formation of voids and dead lithium clusters, and thick passivation interlayers. The analysis also showed that the polyolefin separator has a fundamental role as mechanical barrier in hindering short circuits during cycling.

NMC-811|HCPE|Li cells showed good cycling performance, with specific discharge capacity of 180 mAh g^{-1} at C/10 and $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 150 mAh g^{-1} at C/3, and capacity retention of 82% after 100 cycles. Large NMC-811 | HCPE | Li pouch cells with 1 Ah capacity and higher areal capacity of 2.7 mAh cm^{-2} , showed

Figure 10. Overtemperature test of a 1 Ah solid-state battery cell at 100% SoC: a) temperature versus time profile of the cell and copper plates temperatures, with phase A, the temperature ramp 6 °C min^{-1} , phase B, thermal runaway of the cell, and phase C, cooling of the cell. b–e) Digital images of the abusive test sequence: b) $t = 0$ s (t_{ini}) wide field, ejection of the first incandescent particles; c) $t = 4$ s, ($T = T_{max}$) wide field of the thermal runaway; d) $t = 7$ s, end of thermal runaway, beginning of cooling (phase c); e) photo of the abused cell.

initial capacity of 150 mAh g^{-1} and capacity retention of 80% after 110 cycles, at 60 °C and C-rate of C/10. These cells showed energy density of 246 Wh kg^{-1} , close to state-of-the-art LIBs. Detailed EIS analysis was conducted on a solid-state NMC|HCPE|Li single-layer pouch cell, instrumented with a LFP reference electrode. At the cell level, the EIS profiles present three main resistances at specific frequency ranges (10^5 – 10^4 Hz, 10^4 – 100 Hz, 100 Hz– 100 mHz). Despite the insertion of LFP reference, similar EIS spectra were obtained compared to the non-instrumented cell. This result strongly implies that the

reference electrode does not cause major artefacts on the EIS measurements. Besides, EIS profiles from the positive and negative electrodes were successfully monitored over cycling and first assumptions on their main resistive contributions were proposed. This allowed identifying the cathode charge transfer resistance as the main contribution to the overall cell impedance.

Finally, an overtemperature test was performed on the 1 Ah solid state cell. This preliminary safety assessment showed that advantageously, the solid-state technology developed in this study

with Li metal anode, solid electrolyte, and no safety devices delivers similar performance to commercial high energy 18650 cells with liquid electrolyte and conventional electrodes (graphite anode and Ni-rich cathode).

This study presents one of the first examples of cycling performance and safety testing for high-voltage polymer batteries (HV-LPBs) at a multi-layer 1 Ah cell level and with practical cell configuration (high cathode loading and a thin lithium anode). As such, it underscores the potential and challenges of high-voltage polymer battery technology. Focusing on the strengths, this study demonstrates that HV-LPBs can easily achieve the highest values of energy density achievable by LIBs, even in small-scale, non-optimized cell configurations. Furthermore, the safety characteristics are comparable to those of LIBs, despite the use of highly reactive Li metal electrodes. This is a positive effect of using polymer electrolytes, although it also shows that the use of polymer electrolytes does not totally hinder the occurrence of thermal run-aways. Regarding the limitations, the energy density is still below the target for the automotive sector (400 Wh kg⁻¹ or higher), despite the use of relatively high cathode loadings and of 40 μm-thin, current collector-free lithium metal anodes (equivalent to 20 μm-thin lithium electrodes per cell). In addition, the cyclability, rate capability, and operational temperature are still high, when compared to those of commercial LIBs. The cycle life is affected by the progressive increase of the overall cell resistance, mainly caused by the increase of the cathode charge transfer resistance and by the degradation of the lithium/electrolyte interface, as indicated by the EIS study and by the postmortem SEM analysis, respectively. Thus, improvement of the cycle life will involve further optimization of the anode and cathode interfaces. The enhancement of the C-rate capability and of the operational temperature decreasing will require the use of structured lithium anode and the addition of plasticizers with higher ionic conductivity or liquid electrolytes, that is, the transition toward quasi-solid electrolytes. Achieving the target values of energy density can be achieved through further optimization of the cell configuration, specifically through an increase of the cathode loading (toward areal capacities of 4 mAh cm⁻², or higher, and fractions of cathode active material of 80 wt%), the use of thinner solid electrolytes (50 μm or lower), and by increasing the charge cut-off voltage, to enhance the cathode active material utilization. On the other hand, all these measures need to be carefully balanced considering the inevitable trade-off with the C-rate capability and cycle life.

4. Experimental Section

Mechanically Reinforced Composite Electrolyte Preparation: The hybrid ceramic polymer electrolytes (HCPE) were composed of an ethylene oxide-propylene oxide copolymer (p(EO-co-PO) $M_w \approx 800$ kg mol⁻¹), poly(ethylene glycol) dimethyl ether (PEGDME, $M_n \approx 500$ g mol⁻¹, Merck) as polymer plasticizer and a cross-linker poly(ethylene diacrylate) (PEGDA, $M_n \approx 700$ g mol⁻¹, Merck). The electrolytes were prepared in an argon-filled glove box. A 5 vol% of Li_{1+x}Al_xTi_{2-x}(PO₄)₃ (LATP, Schott) was dispersed in the polyether-based matrix. First, the polymer matrix components (p(EO-co-PO), PEGDME, and PEGDA), lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide LiTFSI (Solvionic, in a molar ratio EO:Li = 16) and LATP were mixed overnight in acetonitrile (ACN) under rigorous stirring. The next day, the initiator azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN,

Merck) was added to the solution. The solution was then milled with a Micro Pulverisette 7 premium planetary (Fritsch). Hermetically sealed 45 mL zirconium flasks were used, which were loaded and sealed in argon atmosphere with 5 mm diameter ZrO₂ beads. The total wet milling time was 20 min at 250 rpm, interrupted by a 10 min pause to avoid overheating of the system. The homogeneous solutions were cast on a Celgard 2500 separator, with a target dry thickness of 70 μm. The ACN was first evaporated for 3 h at room temperature and then at 70 °C for one hour at 500 mbar, to complete the cross-linking step. In this step, an interpenetrating acrylate polymer network was formed. Prior to characterization, the membranes were dried under dynamic vacuum overnight.

Positive Electrode Preparation: Unsupported HCPEs were tested with low-loading cathodes, composed of 80 wt% active material (NMC-811, Umicore), 10 wt% C65 conductive carbon (Imerys) and 10 wt% catholyte (23 wt% LiTFSI respect to PVdF + 2 vol% LATP). The insoluble components were dispersed by milling in a LiTFSI/PVdF/N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) solution (20 min mixing at 250 rpm, interrupted by a 10 min pause) and the resulting slurry was cast by conventional method. The cathodes were dried first under low vacuum (200 mbar), overnight, and at 50 °C, and then again under higher vacuum (1 mbar), overnight, at 50 °C. The areal loading of active material was ≈ 1 mAh cm⁻².

Supported HCPEs were tested with the following optimized cathode formulations. Positive electrodes based on NMC-811 contained 74 wt% of NMC-811 as active material, 3 wt% of C45 carbon black (Imerys) as conductive additive, and 23 wt% of a catholyte. The positive electrode slurries were prepared at laboratory and pilot plant scale. In both cases, NMP was used as solvent. On the laboratory scale, slurries were prepared using a mechanical mixer. Once all the components of the slurry were perfectly mixed, the slurry was cast on carbon-coated aluminum foil (Gelon) by of a doctor blade applicator and then dried at 60 °C. Afterwards, one-side coated electrode strips were calendered with the use of a laboratory hydraulic roll calender (DPM Solutions) at ambient temperature. In turn, manufacturing of double-sided positive electrodes at pilot plant level was performed using the same materials and current collectors. First, a 2 kg batch slurry was prepared in a 5 L mixer and then the obtained slurry was casted on Al/C foil (Gelon) using continuous roll to roll coating system (Mathis). Afterwards, obtained positive electrode strips were calendered by roll press (Naknor Electrode Rolling Equipment – LDHY400-N45) at ambient temperature. Finally, both types of solid-state positive electrodes were hot-pressed (Laborpresse – Polystat 200T) to achieve the maximum compaction to improve the electrochemical performance. Two types of electrodes were prepared, with active material loadings of 5 and 15.2 mg cm⁻², respectively, corresponding to nominal area capacities of 0.9 and 2.7 mAh cm⁻², calculated with a nominal specific capacity of 180 mAh g⁻¹. More detailed information about the prepared positive electrode was described in Table 3.

Thermal Properties: Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) was completed at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ with an argon flow of 60 mL min⁻¹. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measurement was performed with a DSC 2500 differential calorimeter (TA Instruments). The measurement was carried out by placing a sample of 5 – 10 mg in sealed aluminum pans under argon atmosphere, in the temperature range between –80 °C and 100 °C, and with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The sample was cycled twice between –80 °C and 100 °C, and the second heating scan was used for the analysis. The mechanical properties of the HCPE were studied by tensile test, with an Instron, 345C-5 single column universal testing machine, equipped with a 100 N 2519 Series S-beam static load cell. The samples had a width of 10 mm, whereas the separation between the clamps was ≈ 10 mm. A displacement speed of 20 cm min⁻¹ was used in the measurements.

Transport Properties: Ionic conductivity was measured by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) with a Solartron 1260A Impedance/Gain-Phase Analyzer, in the frequency range comprised between 32 MHz and 1 Hz (20 points per decade), with a signal amplitude of 20 mV, and in the temperature, range comprised between 20 and

80 °C. The measurements were carried out in coin cells CR2032, with stainless steel electrodes. The temperature was controlled with a Binder KB23 incubator. The ionic conductivity was calculated with the following equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R} \frac{L}{A} \quad (1)$$

where R is the bulk electrolyte resistance, A is the electrodes surface area and L is the membrane thickness. The latter was measured with a digital micrometer after the experiment. The measurement was repeated on three replicas.

The Li^+ transference number (T^+) at 60 °C was determined by potentiostatic polarization method, with a Biologic VMP3 potentiostat. Three symmetric Li||Li coin cells were subjected to polarization of 10 mV and the resulting current recorded for 20 min. The current was recorded with a frequency of ten points per second during the first minute, and of one point per second during the remaining time. EIS spectra were collected before and after the polarization. The measurement was repeated six times on each cell, by alternating positive and negative polarizations. The resulting transference number was thus averaged over eighteen measurements. The transference number was calculated by applying equations 2) (Bruce-Vincent method) and 3) (Watanabe method).^[49,50]

$$T_{BV}^+ = \frac{I_{SS}}{I_0} \frac{(\Delta V - I_0 R_{2,0})}{(\Delta V - I_{SS} R_{2,SS})} \quad (2)$$

$$T_{Wat}^+ = R_1 / (\Delta V / I_{SS} - R_{2,SS}) \quad (3)$$

where I_0 and I_{SS} are the initial and steady-state currents, respectively, ΔV the voltage polarization, R_1 the high-frequency resistance in the EIS spectra, $R_{2,0}$ and $R_{2,SS}$ the initial and steady-state low-frequency resistances, respectively.

The Li/electrolyte interface resistance at 60 °C was determined from the EIS spectra performed during the transference number experiments, by the following formula:

$$R_{int} = \frac{R_2 A}{2} \quad (4)$$

where A was the electrodes area.

The restricted diffusion coefficient (D) at 60 °C was determined by recording the voltage relaxation at the end of each potentiostatic polarization and by applying the following formula:^[51]

$$D = -b \frac{L^2}{\pi^2} \quad (5)$$

where b is the slope of lnV versus time.

Morphological and Elemental Characterization: Morphology and elemental composition of sample cross-sections were studied by combining the ion milling technique, FESEM micrographs and the acquisition of FESEM-EDX elemental mappings. Cross-sectioning was performed on the Hitachi 4000 Plus ion milling (XIM) which produces wider, undistorted cross section milling without applying mechanical stress to the sample. Considering the samples' sensitivity to the environment, a special XIM module for avoiding exposition had been implemented. In this way, samples were transferred between the glovebox, the ion milling and the SEM, under argon atmosphere. Moreover, to reduce the possible damage coming from the interaction between the ionic beam and the materials in the sample (organic layers and lithium), XIM technique was performed at -70 °C by introducing a cryogenic module.

After cross-sectioning, samples were transferred directly to the APREO 2 S HiVac FESEM by means of the XIM sealed transfer module. The APREO 2 S was a Schottky Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope that combines high- and low-voltages and ultrahigh resolution capabilities. The APREO 2 S FESEM expands to analytical capability by integrating a Thermo

Scientific Windowless EDX detector. This technology counts with enough spectral resolution to detect light elements, such as the Li-K edge, and integrates compositional mapping option for analyzing simultaneously the distribution of different elements on the observed surface. From the acquired elemental EDX mappings and by means of the COMPASS images processing algorithm, included in the EDX controller software, the different phases present in the samples had been identified and exposed over the SEM micrographs.

Electrochemical Stability: The oxidative stability of the electrolytes was measured by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) at 60 °C, in stainless-steel (SS)||Li coin cells, by performing scans up to 6.0 V versus Li/Li⁺, with a scan rate of 0.1 mV s⁻¹. The chemical and electrochemical stability in contact with the positive electrode, at 60 °C, was further investigated by means of cyclic voltammetry (CV), EIS, and by floating current test in NMC-811||Li cells. In the CV experiment, an NMC-811||Li cell was cycled between the OCV and 4.3 V at 20 μV s⁻¹ at 60 °C. Five cycles were performed to check the reversibility of the redox process in this voltage range. In the EIS experiments, a cell was charged galvanostatically at C/20 up to 4.3 V. The cell voltage was then kept constant at 4.3 V and EIS spectra were collected at intervals of one hour for 12 h. In the floating current test, an NMC-811||Li coin cell was charged galvanostatically at C/20, up to 4.3 V. Subsequently, the voltage was kept constant at 4.3 V for 10 h and then increased stepwise up to 5.0 V, with step interval of 100 mV and step duration of 10 h.

Pouch Cells Assembling: The pouch cell with nominal capacity of 1 Ah has been manually assembled by stacking several 50 × 60 mm² cell units composed by a double sided NMC-811 positive electrode, a HCPE membrane and a Li metal negative electrode. The design of the cell and the assembly procedure had been optimized to maximize both the energy density and the electrochemical performance. First, the cathode was wrapped in solid electrolyte, and afterwards, the laminated cathode was placed over the anode. The number of electrodes varies depending on the cell capacity. Thus, for 1 Ah pouch cell assembling, six cathode sheets and seven lithium metal foils were stacked together. At last, the stack was covered with the cell cover and the obtained stack was placed-stacked on the pouch film (see assembling procedure in Figure S1a, Supporting Information). It must be noted that pouch cell format with no safety devices was used to assess the intrinsic properties of the cell chemistry.

Three-Electrode Measurements on a Solid-State NMC-811/HCPE/Li Single-Layer Pouch Cell: Partially delithiated LFP reference electrode (open circuit potential: 3.424 V versus Li) was inserted in a three-electrode single-layer solid-state pouch cell to monitor separately the potential evolution from the NMC-811 positive electrode and Li metal negative electrode. The potential of LFP reference electrode was set at the middle of the potential plateau of LFP (Li_{0.5}FePO₄) before its introduction within the cell. This allows having a reference electrode immediately functional. The reference electrode was placed between Li metal electrode and HCPE during the cell assembly and protected with a pristine polymer electrolyte layer. Single-layer pouch cells assembly with reference electrode (three-electrode cell) and without any reference electrode (two-electrode cell), was exclusively carried out in a dry room (dew point: -40 °C). The single-layer pouch cells were then pressed under 3 kg cm⁻² using a home-made set-up for cycling and the specific capacity of 11 mAh, considering 180 mAh g⁻¹ for the NMC-811 based solid-state electrode.

The evolution of the interphases at the positive and negative electrodes was evaluated by performing EIS at several potentials during charge and discharge or consequently at distinct states of charge (SoC). The cells were cycled at 60 °C at 0.28 mA cm⁻² equivalent to C/10, between 4.2 and 3.0 V, with 12 h of rest beforehand. Cycles with and without EIS steps were alternated. EIS measurements were conducted on a Bio-Logic VMP-300 modular potentiostat/galvanostat, from 7 MHz to 100 mHz (13 points per decade), by using a signal amplitude of 10 mV. CV steps (with limited intensity, equivalent to C/10), followed by a two hour-relaxation step, were performed before launching each EIS. A Binder KB23 was used as temperature chamber.

Safety Test: The aim of the abuse test was to cause the thermal runaway of a fully charged 1 Ah-cell (with dimensions of 105×82×1 mm³, mass of 16.03 g, resistance of 1.1 Ω) by heating in overtemperature

conditions, and to measure thermal runaway features. For the abusive test, the cell described above was sandwiched between two copper plates (117×80×5 mm³, 830 g each, Figure S1b–d, Supporting Information). A heating pad was assembled by placing a Ni-Cr wire (0.35 mm diameter, 15 Ω) within two layers of ceramic tape (Figure S1b, Supporting Information). Then, the pad was placed between the cell and one of the copper plates. A thermal insulation layer was added between the pad and the copper plate, to prevent heat loss during the heating phase. The plates were bolted together at 0.35 N m, to create a compressed sandwich containing the cell (Figure S1c, Supporting Information). Finally, this stack was thermally insulated with a fiberglass-textile coating (Figure S1d, Supporting Information). Six thermocouples were used, two on the cell and two on each copper plate. All the thermocouples were used to calculate the energy released by the cell during thermal runaway. The heat release Q_+ (kJ) was calculated from the plate enthalpy using equation 6), where m_{plate} was the mass of the calorimeter (kg), c_{p_plate} was the mean plate specific heat capacity, ΔT_{plate} was the temperature change of the plate (K), and $Q_{heating}$ was the heating energy applied to the cell (kJ).

$$Q_+ = m_{plate} \cdot c_{p_plate} \cdot \Delta T_{plate} - Q_{heating} \quad (6)$$

For the overtemperature test, the cell was preliminarily introduced in a reinforced 1 m³-vessel, heated and maintained at 60 °C for several hours (the resistance dropped to 0.21 Ω at 60 °C), before being slowly charged at 40 mA until reaching full capacity (4.2 V – 1.01 Ah) with an Arbin BT200, always at 60 °C. A pressure sensor (RS Pro – IPSL series – 50 mbar) was added within the vessel.

The abuse test started with a controlled heating phase with a slope of 6 °C min⁻¹. The power was finely controlled with a power supply (EA – EL 9080-60 DT – 1200 W) and sent to the heating pad until thermal runaway occurred.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

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